

A STUDY ON EVALUATING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF RUNWAY SAFETY MONITORING MECHANISMS IN SRI LANKA AIR FORCE

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Abstract - Aviation safety is a crucial concern from the ground preparation itself since many factors are associated with flight operations rather than the phases of flight. In this context, proper maintenance of runways could not be neglected at any cost when ensuring aviation safety considerations. To ascertain the same, validated runway monitoring mechanisms are required, since such mechanisms would provide insights for the decision makers at strategic levels to visualize the concerns through monitored trends. SLAF being the sole military aviation arm of the country plays a pivotal role in this context as it maintains many domestic runways which are being used for military as well as domestic air transportation and flying training purposes. Thus, this study aims to identify the effectiveness of present runway condition monitoring mechanisms in SLAF in order to identify the prevailing gaps. A qualitative study is carried out whilst Ops Air branch officers who perform duties as Senior Air Traffic Controlling Officers (SATCO) in SLAF establishments considering as the sample of the study. Further, the interviews conducted with the participation of them were considered as primary data. A thematic analysis is conducted with use of primary and secondary data to evaluate available measures within SLAF giving more prominence to technological aspects based on findings. In this context, it was identified

that available mechanisms are comparatively lesser effective when considered with the available measures in the global context. Thus, applicable improvements are suggested to enable proactive management of Air Force assets and operations emphasizing the integration of technology for smart initiatives in SLAF.

Key words: Runway monitoring, Flight Safety, Runway Safety

INTRODUCTION

1. Aviation safety is a crucial concern from the ground preparation itself since many factors are associated with flight operations rather than the phases of flight. In this context, proper maintenance and monitoring of runways could not be neglected at any cost when ensuring aviation safety considerations. To ascertain the same, validated runway monitoring mechanisms are required, since such mechanisms would provide insights for the decision makers at strategic levels to visualize the concerns through monitored trends in order to ensure proper maintenance and monitoring of runways.

2. Sri Lanka Air Force (SLAF) being the sole military aviation arm of the country plays a pivotal role in this context as it

maintains many domestic runways which are being used for military as well as domestic air transportation and flying training purposes. Hence, it has become a prime responsibility of SLAF to safeguard and well maintain these infrastructures for safer aviation operation within the country undoubtedly.

3. Thus, this study aims to identify the effectiveness of present runway safety monitoring mechanisms of SLAF in order to identify the prevailing gaps.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

4. As runway safety is a major concern which aligns with safer flight operations, many measures have been implemented to ensure hazard free operational environment. Thus, SLAF being a major stakeholder in the flight operations in Sri Lankan context, has introduced many safety practices and procedures which are suitable for local considerations incorporating with international standards.

5. However, it is required to evaluate these procedures as a timely requirement in order to identify the gaps of the same to enhance the effectiveness of these including any newer measure is identified.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

6. In this context, the main objective of this research study is to identify prevailing mechanisms of runway safety monitoring while identifying the limitations encountering during the execution of such mechanisms. Further, it is expected to

introduce measures to overcome identified limitations with regard to this concern.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

7. Thus, research questions of this study are as follows.

a. What are the prevailing mechanisms of runway safety monitoring in practice in SLAF?

b. What are the limitations encountered when executing these mechanisms?

c. What measures could be implemented to overcome these limitations?

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE RESEARCH

8. The significance of this research lies in:

a. **Safety Enhancement.**

By evaluating monitoring mechanisms, it could be contributed to safer runways, reducing the risk of incidents during take-off and landing.

b. **Operational Efficiency.**

Effective monitoring streamlines maintenance efforts, minimizing runway closures and delays.

9. **Cost Savings.** Accurate assessments lead to targeted repairs,

optimizing comprehensive resource allocation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

9. Accidents seem inevitable, but measures could be implemented to mitigate such occurrences. As per statistics, most of the aviation accidents are occurred during landing and take-off phases due to various concerns.

Figure 01: Aviation Accidents 2005 - 2023
Source: www.statista.com, www.iata.com

10. Many reasons lead to aircraft accidents or incident such as human error, equipment failure, material failure, technical problems, internal object damage, foreign object ingestion, wild life and bird strike, weather and pilot error, etc. Out of such, several investigations into these accidents highlighted the ingestion of foreign object into propulsion systems and wild life strike are major reasons that paved its way towards catastrophic occurrences (Nurenberg Paris, 2017).

11. Foreign object debris could be loose objects, small debris, wildlife, and even

stray humans (Patterson Jr, 2008). As indicated below, foreign object debris can be categorized under different possible types. Further, in aviation FOD has two connotations:

- a. Foreign Object Debris
- b. Foreign Object Damage

FOD types	Sources
Personnel	Caused by inappropriate housekeeping and poor working behavior.
Infrastructure	Pavements, lights, and signs
Materials	Paint chips, rubber joint, asphalt and concrete chunks
Environment	Ice, snow, and wildlife
Operating Equipment	Ground Handling vehicles and construction equipment
Aircraft parts	Tire fragments, trapdoors, oil stick, and fuel cap
Fasteners	Washers, bolts, and nuts
Flight Line Items	Luggage tags, personnel badges, cans

Figure 02: FOD (Debris) types and sources
Source: Khan et al (2020)

12. Foreign Object Damage; accidents and incidents incur due to foreign object debris. Thus, debris removal from designated areas is mandatorily required to prevent FOD as per the guidelines provided by aviation authorities. Area sensitivity can be considered for prioritization as per following diagram.

Figure 03: Consequences of FOD (Debris)
Source: Khan et al (2020)

Figure 04: Runway Safety Related Accidents 2019-2023

Source: www.icao.int

13. In that context, runway is a crucial concern in aviation safety as it is where landing and leaving aircraft may have the chance to encounter with other taxiing aircraft, ground vehicles, people, animals, and foreign objects.

14. Due to the aircraft's high speed and limited capacity to avoid obstacles on the runway, particularly during take-off and landing, many nations are deeply concerned about the possible hazards that runway incursions or the presence of foreign objects could pose to aviation safety. Many studies have contributed in this cause emphasizing the importance of safety of the runway.

RUNWAY SAFETY

15. Runway safety includes all the concerns with the identification and prevention of hazards that might hinder the safe take off, taxiing and landing at an aerodrome of all types of aircraft whereas following areas such as Airport Surface Management & Safety, Runway Incursion prevention, Local Runway Safety Teams, Training for Airport Surface Operations, Aerodrome Resource Management etc (skybrary.aero, n.d.).

16. Furthermore, it is defined as ‘The state in which risks associated with the operation of aircraft on runways are reduced and controlled to an acceptable level.’ (ICAO, 2015)

17. Moreover, as emphasized in ICAO annex 14, an airport must implement a maintenance schedule, including preventative maintenance as needed, to keep the runway in a condition that does not endanger aircraft operations whereas a rigorous maintenance program should be designed to prevent failure or degradation of runway facilities (SLCAP 2150).

18. In addition, the surface of pavements (runways and nearby areas) must be free of loose stones or other debris that could harm aircraft structures or engines or interfere with aviation system functions. In this regard, a complete runway inspection and sweeping program should be incorporated into the routine operation procedures of the aerodrome operator (SLCAP 2150).

PREVAILING RUNWAY SAFETY MECHANISMS

19. In present context, manual foreign object detection drills are practiced on many airports and military air force bases. As per guidelines of Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) and the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO), ‘the airline personnel, when feasible, should join the airport staff in daily, daylight inspection of aircraft manoeuvring areas for removal of FOD (Khan et al., 2020). In order to control the FOD (debris) in the civil or military airports, ICAO has published procedures which are to be

followed have been categorized into four sections:

- a. Training
- b. Inspection
- c. Maintenance
- d. Coordination

20. However, conduct of manual detection drills are not practicable when the traffic is heavier. Thus, to address this impracticality many aviation researches have been conducted and as a result, many automated mechanisms have been introduced based on remote sensing (with use of millimetre wave radar, optical cameras, laser range finder, photoelectric encoder, data fusion device and LiDAR based autonomous vehicle), heat detection mechanisms while others use high definition video surveillance to locate and report debris. Many of these mechanisms currently in use and practice in order to minimize accidents and incidents during landing and take-off phases of flight.

Figure 04: LiDAR detection flow diagram
Source: Khan et al (2020)

21. As demonstrated by Khan et al., (2020), a foreign object detection and alert

system has been developed as a prototype with use of LiDAR technology which can be used to identify small objects as suggests by the study. Same has been tested in lab conditions for various types and sizes of objects and has proven successful on detection.

22. Maximum and accurate imaging technology is required for rapid and precise identification of foreign object debris on runways as stressed by (Kohmura et al., 2013). Further, as stressed in this study, optical fiber linked with millimeter-wave Radar system would be effective for larger airports which has proven experimentally. Further, it is mentioned that uses of 2D algorithms in W-band (75-110 GHz) for modeling of foreign object debris (Kanno and Kawanishi, 2013).

23. In the extensive study carried out by Khan et al. (2017), it has been highlighted that detection systems could provide false alarms. Thus, a detection system has been developed and proven with results with Maximally Stable Extremal Region (MSER) algorithms to minimize false alarm rates on detections in which this system includes with mode selection, sensing and scanning phase, image processing and communication components.

24. In addition, Wildlife Hazard Management (WHM) system is considered as key component of maintenance services of any airport whereas certain guidelines have been issued by ICAO to minimize the impacts of wildlife strikes on the surface or vicinity of the airport. Addressing this concern, Dziak et al., (2022) have presented a solution based on sensor fusion approach in this prototype of the system produced has

provided results combining thermal and vision images ensuring risk mitigation during day and night. As per this study, the particular system has attained 92% of efficiency for small objects (eg: Dogs) at a distance of 300m whilst indicating 92% efficiency for larger objects (eg: Humans) at a distance of 325m.

25. Moreover, when pavement conditions are concerned with regard to runway safety, the study conducted by Huang et al., (2004) emphasizes that incorporation of GIS and GPS into pavement management system (PMS) has a lot of benefits. Specially, distress data can be stored in a well-designed geographical database, whereas complex queries and analyses will be available for managers to optimize pavement maintenance.

26. Furthermore, GIS can also help to envisage the distress data stored in the database which adds geographical dimension to the tabular data and hence it adds more value to the data. This connotation is stressed by Grotefend, (2017) in his study whilst emphasizing the importance of incorporating web GIS application which allows decision makers to visualize the situations easily to imply and execute the better and timely decisions.

27. As discussed by Chung et al., (2004), an automated in-situ road surface distress surveying and management system, has been developed based on video images to be compatible with the framework of GIS software. Some provide efficient visualizations which present user-friendly interfaces in GIS and surveyed results are available for the stakeholders of the operation to further evaluate the socio-economic impacts of degradation and

deterioration. Further, as indicates by this study, it is evident that the proposed approach of using GIS concept and its tools for PMS application will reshape PMS into a new information technology-based system that can provide convenient and efficient pavement inspection and management.

METHODOLOGY

28. A qualitative study is carried out whilst Ops Air branch officers who perform duties as Senior Air Traffic Controlling Officers (SATCO) in SLAF establishments considering as the sample of the study. Further, the interviews conducted with the participation of them considered as primary data. With that, a thematic analysis is conducted with use of primary and secondary data to evaluate available measures within SLAF giving more prominence to technological aspects based on findings.

FINDINGS

29. As per the interviews conducted, following findings were made based on thematic analysis method.

PREVAILING RUNWAY SAFETY MONITORING MECHANISMS IN SLAF

30. In this context, following themes were identified with regard to the concerns on prevailing runway safety mechanisms in SLAF from the conducted interviews.

a. **Routine Maintenance and Safety Procedures.** As per the interviewees explanations during the interviews, routine maintenance is being carried out in SLAF runways and applicable safety procedures are implemented. However, this is mostly in terms of locally implemented standard operating procedures. Moreover, though routine maintenance is included various practices such as; removing rubber from the runway, cleaning and replacing light systems, repainting runway markings and evaluating the structural integrity, SLAF is mostly focussed on minor routine maintenance practices whereas major routine maintenance practices are encountered with many constraints. Further, it was identified that there is no effective mechanism to monitor surface conditions and structural integrity in order to furnish required data for a trend analysis.

b. **Daily Operational Checks.** When daily operational checks are concerned, this is being carried out routinely. Specially, routine FOD checks throughout the day in aircraft movement areas, availability of wild life activity controllers along the runway shoulders during flight operations are being carried out can be highlighted with regard to this concern.

c. **Occupancy Management.** Occupancy management of the runway and apron areas is

carefully handled with effective communication practices. All the personnel have been briefed and measures have been introduced to restrict the movements and occupancy as and when required as per prevailing standards.

31. Thus, when prevailing safety monitoring mechanisms are concerned, it is identified that SLAF relies on traditional safety monitoring techniques in present context.

SUITABILITY OF PREVAILING MECHANISMS IN PAR WITH AVIATION STANDARDS IN PRESENT CONTEXT

32. Then, suitability of prevailing mechanisms was questioned in par with aviation standards in present context and following concerns were identified in this regard.

- a. Continuity of safety monitoring mechanisms.
- b. Need of technological advancement.
- c. Compliance with standards and mandatory inspections.
- d. Assessment of current systems.

33. Thus, it was recognized that prevailing mechanisms fulfil only the basic requirements of safety monitoring mechanisms whereas many implementations are required to be done to be in par with present day context standards

and such implementations would uplift the effectiveness of the runway safety monitoring mechanisms.

CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED WHEN EXECUTING PREVAILING MECHANISMS

34. Furthermore, it was identified that there are considerable number of challenges when executing the mechanisms which are currently in practice.

a. **Manpower.** For traditional techniques of safety monitoring mechanisms which are in practice in SLAF, it requires higher number of manpower to ensure smooth operation. However, with the concerns on downsizing the force, this matter has reached to a crucial stage as of the inadequacy of required number of teams to ensure effective safety monitoring mechanisms.

b. **Resources and Technological Limitations.**

Moreover, due to financial and other unspecified constraints, allocation of available resources and induction of novel technological aspects has been considered as a challenge with regard to the prevailing mechanisms.

c. **Non-Aviation Utilization of Runway.** Nevertheless, despite unavailability of required resources, use of runways for non-aviation use has been identified as a challenge since such acts would disrupt the

availability of runways sooner than expected life duration.

d. **Risk of Human Error and Outdated Systems.** In addition, as of the dearth of man power, more chances on errors could be expected on human error aspect as of the increased work load and unavailability of adequate rest. Further, use of almost obsolete systems would lead unavoidable delays in repairs and thus particular functions would rely completely with human involvement which would ultimately lead to human errors.

MEASURES TO ENHANCE EFFECTIVENESS OF RUNWAY SAFETY MONITORING MECHANISMS

35. In this context, following measures were highlighted as the measures to enhance the effectiveness of runway safety monitoring mechanisms as stressed during the interviews.

a. **Automation and Computerization.** Since SLAF depends on traditional techniques of runway safety monitoring, it requires substantial strength of man power and same has identified as a major challenge in present context. Further, there would be many occurrences that would be easily neglected as of the human tendency and sometimes human intervention would not be sufficient to overlook the situation which requires detailed attention such as runway surface

condition monitoring for a longer period of time. In that aspect, automation and computerization would improve accuracy while enhancing the effectiveness of safety monitoring mechanisms. Further, computerization of data would provide insights for the decision makers to prioritize the tasks as required.

b. **Advanced Monitoring Technologies.** Since it is only monitoring through human involvements, there would be many lapses that would ultimately lead to catastrophic situations. Thus, availability of advanced monitoring systems would ensure effective outcome with real-time data which is more focussed with the lesser human interaction. Specially, such monitoring systems would be beneficial for night operations where human involved monitoring is extremely limited.

c. **Exclusive Aviation Use and implementation of best practices.** Since SLAF has limited capability to maintain all the runways in optimum conditions, allowing runways exclusively for aviation use would further preserve the life of the runways than its use of non-aviation activities. Moreover, amalgamating best practices of SLCAP 2150 along with SLAF SOPs would further ensure effective utilization of runways within the enhanced safety culture of the organization.

ANALYSIS

36. Based on the primary and secondary data, following can be highlighted.

a. In terms of runway safety monitoring mechanisms including wildlife management and surface condition monitoring, SLAF solely depends on traditional and preliminary approach which is acceptable, but which consumes lot of resources and energy whilst unavailability of trend monitoring measure could be considered as a huge drawback.

b. Moreover, as the mechanisms utilize by SLAF mostly relies on human intervention, possibilities remain higher for human errors.

c. However, there are many simplest to advanced systems available, experimentally proven and currently utilizing in global context as effective runway monitoring mechanisms whilst ensuring data is recorded for future references and to monitor trends for further analysis.

37. Thus, it can be declared that the mechanisms available in SLAF to monitor runway safety are comparatively lesser effective in par with present day context.

RECOMMENDATIONS

38. Based on findings and analysis, following recommendations are made.

a. An automated runway monitoring mechanism could be introduced based on suitable technology (Ex: LiDAR technology) which would be affordable for SLAF. This would minimize the human and physical resource utilization for routine FOD checks, management of wildlife hazards etc.

b. In order to analyse the trends of runway surface degradation and to propose timely effective remedial actions, introduction of periodical surveys with the application of drones and GIS and RS would provide enhanced access for decision makers whilst eventually ensuring runway safety mechanisms in SLAF.

FUTURE RESEARCHES

39. Future studies pertaining to this concern could be conducted to identify most feasible solutions for SLAF in terms of automated runway safety monitoring systems with use of suitable technology.

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